

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
globalbioticinteractions/psuc-ento
hash://md5/f94fa2cc2e1edc339d5e63790a56c7f2

by Nomer, Elton and Preston, three naive review bots
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<https://globalbioticinteractions.org/contribute>
<https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/psuc-ento/issues>

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Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named globalbioticinteractions/psuc-ento, has fingerprint hash://md5/f94fa2cc2e1edc339d5e63790a56c7f2, is 15.7MiB in size and contains 71,990 interactions with 7 unique types of associations (e.g., interactsWith) between 1,937 primary taxa (e.g., *Augochlora pura*) and 1,309 associated taxa (e.g., *Prunus*). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

Frost Entomological Museum, Pennsylvania State University
<https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/psuc-ento/archive/30b1f96619a6e9f10da18b42fb93ff22cc4f722026-01-24T05:48:38.541Z> hash://md5/f94fa2cc2e1edc339d5e63790a56c7f2

For additional metadata related to this dataset, please visit <https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/psuc-ento> and inspect associated metadata files including, but not limited to, *README.md*, *eml.xml*, and/or *globi.json*.

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.1
nomer	0.5.17
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 15.7MiB) under review
elton pull globalbioticinteractions/psuc-ento

# generate review notes
elton review globalbioticinteractions/psuc-ento\
> review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/psuc-ento\
> interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names globalbioticinteractions/psuc-ento\
| nomer append col\
> name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull globalbioticinteractions/psuc-ento`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review globalbioticinteractions/psuc-ento`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/psuc-ento`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names globalbioticinteractions/psuc-ento`)

You can find a copy of the full review script at `check-data.sh`. See also GitHub and Codeberg.

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
<code>biblio.bib</code>	list of bibliographic reference of this review
<code>check-dataset.sh</code>	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
<code>data.zip</code>	a versioned archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
<code>index.docx</code>	review in MS Word format
<code>index.html</code>	review in HTML format
<code>index.md</code>	review in Pandoc markdown format
<code>index.pdf</code>	review in PDF format
<code>indexed-citations.csv.gz</code>	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
<code>indexed-citations.html.gz</code>	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
<code>indexed-citations.tsv.gz</code>	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format
<code>indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg</code>	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

filename	description
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format

filename	description
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

Biotic Interactions

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/psuc-ento`, has fingerprint hash://md5/f94fa2cc2e1edc339d5e63790a56c7f2, is 15.7MiB in size and contains 71,990 interactions with 7 unique types of associations (e.g., `interactsWith`) between 1,937 primary taxa (e.g., *Augochlora pura*) and 1,309 associated taxa (e.g., *Prunus*).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped `csv`, `tsv`, `geopackage` and `parquet` archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped `html` page at `indexed-interactions.html.gz` are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

Table 3: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
PSUC ENTO http://grbio.org/cool/29fv-ztxs PSUC_FEM_7144 db73d8c6-4525-4e5d-b50b-2d07eaa383b4	<code>interactsWith</code>	Prarie dog	https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/collections/individual/index
Hybophthirus notophallus	<code>interactsWith</code>	Cape Ant Bear or Aardvark	https://scan-bugs.org:443/portal/collections/individual/index

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
PSUC ENTO http://grbio.org/cool/29fv- ztxs PSUC_FEM_7082 a61a4049-6127- 40b6-9789- 9220c144ac3d	interactsWith	Ovis dalli	https://scan- bugs.org:443/portal/collections/individual/index
PSUC ENTO http://grbio.org/cool/29fv- ztxs PSUC_FEM_7083 9d7d60df-b703- 4e2f-9d2d- 04f36990229b	interactsWith	Ovis dalli	https://scan- bugs.org:443/portal/collections/individual/index

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
interactsWith	70737
hasHost	645
adjacentTo	575
eats	25
hostOf	5
visits	2
parasiteOf	1

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Augochlora pura	12396
Ceratina calcarata	7022
Eucera hamata	6564
Bombus impatiens	3922
Apis mellifera	3382
Lasioglossum pilosum	3071
Melissodes bimaculatus	2829
Bombus vagans	2569
Agapostemon virescens	2566

sourceTaxonName	count
Peponapis pruinosa	1402
Ceratina mikmaqi	1029
Halictus ligatus	1010
Bombus bimaculatus	891
Augochlorella aurata	820
Chauliognathus pensylvanicus	672
Lasioglossum tegulare	653
Bombus perplexus	596
Andrena miserabilis	553
Bombus griseocollis	527

Table 6: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
Prunus	31289
Malus	23658
Agastache Blue Fortune	2233
Rudbeckia Herbstonne	993
Agastache Black Adder	729
Rudbeckia Triloba	603
Homo sapiens	551
Rudbeckia Goldsturm	496
Rubus	489
Nepeta Walker's Low	437
Rudbeckia Fulgida	379
Agastache Foeniculum	334
Monarda	290
Quercus alba	242
Canis	241
-77.702398	190
Callorhinus ursinus	178
Pycnanthemum muticum	158
Nepeta Faassenii	156

Table 7: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Augochlora pura	interactsWith	Malus	7157

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Eucera hamata	interactsWith	Prunus	6279
Augochlora pura	interactsWith	Prunus	4327
Ceratina calcarata	interactsWith	Malus	3463
Ceratina calcarata	interactsWith	Prunus	3335
Lasioglossum pilosum	interactsWith	Prunus	2642
Agapostemon virescens	interactsWith	Prunus	2174
Melissodes bimaculatus	interactsWith	Prunus	2100
Bombus vagans	interactsWith	Malus	1714
Apis mellifera	interactsWith	Prunus	1612
Bombus impatiens	interactsWith	Malus	1419
Bombus impatiens	interactsWith	Prunus	1244
Apis mellifera	interactsWith	Malus	1132
Peponapis pruinosa	interactsWith	Prunus	852
Melissodes bimaculatus	interactsWith	Malus	698
Bombus vagans	interactsWith	Prunus	664
Ceratina mikmaqi	interactsWith	Malus	652
Peponapis pruinosa	interactsWith	Malus	537
Lasioglossum tegulare	interactsWith	Malus	481

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download [svg](#)

You can download the indexed dataset under review at [indexed-interactions.csv.gz](#). A tab-separated file can be found at [indexed-interactions.tsv.gz](#)

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution.

Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at indexed-interactions.gpkg for point data and indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 8: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Baryscapus	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Baryscapus
Bracon	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Bracon
Celastrina	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Celastrina
Chrysis	NONE	col	Chrysis

Table 9: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	1519
col	class	2
col	family	136
col	genus	234
col	kingdom	2
col	nanorder	1
col	order	21
col	parvorder	1
col	phylum	1
col	species	974
col	subfamily	3
col	subgenus	10
col	suborder	1
col	subspecies	16
col	subterclass	1
col	superfamily	5
col	tribe	2
col	variety	5
discoverlife	NA	2647
discoverlife	species	255
gbif	NA	1312
gbif	class	2
gbif	family	142
gbif	form	1
gbif	genus	262
gbif	kingdom	3
gbif	order	21
gbif	phylum	1
gbif	species	1158
gbif	subspecies	26
gbif	variety	11
itis	NA	1492
itis	class	2
itis	division	1
itis	family	136
itis	genus	207
itis	kingdom	2
itis	order	19
itis	species	1012

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
itis	subclass	1
itis	subfamily	5
itis	suborder	8
itis	subspecies	10
itis	superfamily	5
itis	superorder	2
itis	tribe	1
itis	variety	3
mdd	NA	2901
ncbi	NA	1575
ncbi	clade	1
ncbi	class	2
ncbi	cohort	1
ncbi	family	136
ncbi	genus	231
ncbi	infraorder	1
ncbi	kingdom	1
ncbi	order	21
ncbi	species	914
ncbi	subclass	1
ncbi	subfamily	4
ncbi	subgenus	9
ncbi	suborder	3
ncbi	subspecies	3
ncbi	subtribe	1
ncbi	superfamily	5
ncbi	superorder	1
ncbi	tribe	1
pdb	NA	2545
pdb	class	2
pdb	family	133
pdb	genus	129
pdb	infraclass	1
pdb	infraorder	2
pdb	kingdom	2
pdb	order	23
pdb	phylum	1
pdb	species	53
pdb	subfamily	4
pdb	suborder	3
pdb	superfamily	5
pdb	tribe	2
pdb	unranked clade	3
tpt	NA	2778

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
tpt	family	8
tpt	genus	15
tpt	order	4
tpt	species	96
wfo	NA	2595
wfo	family	5
wfo	genus	100
wfo	order	1
wfo	species	197
wfo	subspecies	4
wfo	subtribe	1
wfo	variety	2
worms	NA	2496
worms	family	109
worms	genus	113
worms	kingdom	2
worms	order	19
worms	phylum (division)	1
worms	species	154
worms	subclass	2
worms	suborder	3
worms	subspecies	1
worms	subterclass	1
worms	subtribe	1
worms	superfamily	1
worms	variety	1

Table 10: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1419
col	NONE	1762
col	SYNONYM_OF	354
discoverlife	NONE	3004
discoverlife	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	240
discoverlife	SYNONYM_OF	76

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
discoverlife	HOMONYM_OF	19
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1740
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	752
gbif	NONE	1544
itis	SYNONYM_OF	142
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1430
itis	NONE	1735
mdd	NONE	3218
mdd	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	33
mdd	SYNONYM_OF	1
ncbi	SAME_AS	1379
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	76
ncbi	NONE	1822
ncbi	COMMON_NAME_OF	3
pbdb	NONE	2859
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	387
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	39
tpt	NONE	3119
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	128
tpt	SYNONYM_OF	37
wfo	NONE	2880
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	356
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	73
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	45
worms	NONE	2787
worms	SYNONYM_OF	53
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	481

Table 11: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

catalog name	alignment results
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 12: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-01-28T16:27:48Z	note	source taxon name missing: using institution-Code/collectionCode/collectionId/catalogNumber/occu as placeholder
2026-01-28T16:27:48Z	note	source taxon name missing: using institution-Code/collectionCode/collectionId/catalogNumber/occu as placeholder
2026-01-28T16:27:48Z	note	source taxon name missing: using institution-Code/collectionCode/collectionId/catalogNumber/occu as placeholder
2026-01-28T16:27:48Z	note	source taxon name missing: using institution-Code/collectionCode/collectionId/catalogNumber/occu as placeholder

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

Table 13: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

reviewComment	count
source taxon name missing: using institution-Code/collectionCode/collectionId/catalogNumber/occurrenceId as placeholder	569
found unsupported interaction type with name: [parasitoid of]	78
found unsupported interaction type with name: [inquiline of]	78
target taxon name missing	12

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

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⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

⁵At time of writing (2026-01-28) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: "Open data is data that can be freely used, re-used and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike."

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

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